

Synthesis of 4,6-Bis[5'-substituted-isoxazol-3'-yl]resorcinols as Potential Antifeedants

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RECENTLY, a number of diflavones, diflavanols and dicoumarins derived from 4,6-diacetylresorcinol (1) have been shown to exhibit significant antifeedant activity¹. Literature survey revealed that the synthesis and antifeedant activity of the title compounds have not been reported so far. Therefore, the present investigation reports the synthesis of some new 4,6-bis[5'-substituted-isoxazol-3'-yl]resorcinols with a view to evaluate their antifeedant activity.

- b; o-chlorophenyl
- c; p-chlorophenyl
- d; p-methoxyphenyl
- e; p-methylphenyl
- f; furfuryl
- g; 2-thienyl

4,6-Diacetylresorcinol⁹ (**1**) was condensed with various aldehydes in presence of aqueous KOH at room temperature to yield the corresponding dichalcones^{1,8} (**2a-g**), which in turn were treated with bromine in chloroform to yield the corresponding 4,6-bis[3-substituted-2,3-dibromopropanoyl]resorcinnols (**3a-g**) in good yields. All the compounds gave positive Beilstein's test⁴ for halogens and did not decolourise aqueous KMnO₄. The ir spectra did not show absorption at 960 cm⁻¹ (CH=CH). The alcoholic solution of the tetrabromodichalcones on being refluxed with molar proportion of hydroxylamine hydrochloride and aqueous KOH, followed by acidification, yielded the title compounds. The products were characterised by their analytical and spectral data (Table 1). As a representative case, the spectral identification of 4,6-bis[5'-phenylisoxazol-3'-yl]resorcinol (**4a**) has been discussed (see Experimental).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND ANTIFEEDANT ACTIVITY DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4*

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Antifeedant activity (%)
4a	133	70	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂	80.8
b	128	64	C ₂₄ H ₁₄ O ₄ Cl ₂ N ₂	77.0
c	132	60	C ₂₄ H ₁₄ O ₄ Cl ₂ N ₂	73.0
d	180	68	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₂	69.4
e	135	65	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₂	100
f	122	60	C ₂₀ H ₁₂ O ₆ N ₂	32.7
g	125	62	C ₃₀ H ₁₈ O ₄ S ₂ N ₂	78.5

*All compounds gave satisfactory results for C and H analyses.

All the compounds were screened for their anti-feedant activity¹⁰ (Table 1) and **4e** was found to be most active.

Experimental

Preparation of 2a-g: A mixture of **1** (0.01 mol) and the appropriate aldehyde (0.02 mol) in ethanol (40 ml) was stirred at room temperature for 12 h with aqueous KOH (60% ; 10 ml). The product, obtained on dilution and acidification with dilute HCl, was subjected to column chromatography over silica gel (200 mesh). The benzene-chloroform (8 : 2, v/v) elutions on concentration afforded **2**.

Preparation of 3a-g: To a cold solution of **2** (0.01 mol) in chloroform, Br₂/CHCl₃ (0.02 mol) was added dropwise with constant stirring. The solvent was then removed on a steam-bath. The resulting solid was washed with little cold ether to remove excess of bromine and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. (°C): **3a**=140, **b**=170, **c**=190, **d**=190, **e**=175, **f**=110, **g**=112.

Preparation of 4a-g: Ethanol solution of **3** (0.01 mol) was refluxed with hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.02 mol). After a few minutes 30% aqueous KOH was added to it and refluxing continued till the colour of the reaction mixture turned red with simultaneous deposition of potassium bromide. It

was allowed to stand for 30 min at room temperature, cooled and acidified with dilute HCl. The resulting solid bisisoxazoles were washed and crystallised from alcohol: **4a**, C₂₄H₁₆O₄N₂; $\nu_{\max}$ 3200 (OH), 1620 (C=N), 760 and 690 cm⁻¹ (phenyl); $\lambda_{\max}$ (MeOH) 254 (log ϵ 4.12) and 322 nm (3.85), characteristic of 3,5-diarylisoxazoles⁵⁻⁷; δ (200 MHz; DMSO-d₆) 7.3 and 8.2 (1H, s each, H-2 and H-5 respectively), 7.81 (2H, s, D₂O exchangeable, C-1-OH and C-3-OH), 7.54 (2H, s, 4'-H), 7.59 (6H, m, H-3'', 4'', 5'') and 8.0 (4H, m, H-2'', 6''); m/z 396 (M^+ 2%), 278 (4%), 262 (12), 201 (6), 189 (45), 161 (20) and 117 (100)—the fragmentation pattern being diagnostic of the isoxazole ring^{8,9} and supporting structure **4a**.

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